

The Role of the Military Industrial Complex in Perpetuating the Global War on Terror

Abstract:

This essay in analyzing the role of the Military Industrial Complex in perpetuating inefficiencies in the weapon procurement and catalyzing active conflict, looks at the issue in the context of the Global War on Terror in the period between 2001 and 2016. Adding an ethical element to the thesis statement, it compares the moral accountability of a sovereign state with free agency to act with that of a military contractor, including a private military contractor, with an evident profit-making motive. Looking at lobbying practices like campaign finance donations, the "revolving door" of corporate executives and foreign arms sales practices, the essay aims to develop a nuanced understanding of the working of the military-industrial complex before delving into impact on "militarizing" American foreign policy. While the focus is primarily on the US MIC, the conclusion does briefly touch on the practices of the European MIC and provides recommendations for reform to the system to enable the systemic achievement of long-term military outcomes.

Keywords: Military Industrial Complex, Foreign Policy, Global War on Terror, Moral Accountability.

Introduction:

In his farewell address the 34th President of the United States, Dwight D Eisenhower warned against the “acquisition of unwarranted influence ... by the military industrial complex.”¹ This complex which now comes to encompass a myriad of defense contractors, private military contractors and arms manufacturers, was in a novel stage of its development in 1961. Having come into mainstream conception during the first world war, when industrialization of the arms production industry was used as a method to increase the production of high-tech weapons at a faster rate than those produced by state-owned arms manufacturing factories.² Private Defense Contractors started to play a major role in the Second World War when greater defense funding started to be allocated towards R&D and Private Contractors aided in the creation of more advanced weapons.

This trend continued during the cold war, especially with the creation of the Department of Defense which consisted of civilians. Many of these civilians cycled between working at the Pentagon and in corporates as executives before once again transitioning.³ This sort of interaction enabled greater connections between the government and arms industry. The technological standoff between the two blocs, led to increased defense spending which led to an increase in contracts for these companies and with locus of control over these contracts being with politicians, the lobbying powers of these companies expanded greatly during this period. Major advancements like cruise missiles and other aeronautical innovations were the products of these government contracts; these weapons played a major role in projecting military posture and increasing capability.

Following the positive results produced during the cold war, the Pentagon,” embraced outsourcing, increasing reliance on contractors instead of using military servicemembers or government civilians.” However, this period was also marked by decreased demand for weapons and defence spending. This would have normally implied a decline of the industry, but this effect was counteracted by the consolidation of the industry into a few major companies which had immense clout in the Pentagon.⁴ The consolidation of the industry into the “Big 5” - namely Lockheed Martin, Boeing, Northrop Grumman, Raytheon and General Dynamics – also led to a decrease in the competition for military contracts which had typically been won through a bidding war.

At the turn of the millennium, these companies had positioned themselves at a strategic position to profit from war by becoming an essential component of the national security apparatus. Thus, realizing Eisenhower’s note of caution and the idea of “merchants of death.” This also coincided with the 9/11 Terror Attacks which provided the necessary stimulus which enabled the MIC to maximize their potential to profit from war.

¹ National Archives. “President Dwight D. Eisenhower’s Farewell Address (1961),” July 15, 2024. <https://www.archives.gov/milestone-documents/president-dwight-d-eisenhowers-farewell-address>.

² DeVore, Marc. “Military-Industrial Complexes and Their Variations.” *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Military in Politics*, 27BC. https://research-repository.st-andrews.ac.uk/bitstream/handle/10023/26440/DeVore_Military_Industrial_Complexes_and_Their_Variations_MIP_MSS04_003_.pdf;jsessionid=49DB3CCED8DDCE2031D56CDF4AAC2950?sequence=1.

³ Ibid

⁴ Solomon, Owen. “A Study of Prime Defense Contractor Consolidation Since the 1990s and Its Effects,” 2024. <https://libraetd.lib.virginia.edu>.

The War on Terror:

Following the 9/11 Attack on the World Trade Centre by the terrorist group Al Qaeda, the US Government under the Bush administration sought to wage, “A war against all those who seek to export terror, and a war against those governments that support or shelter them.”⁵ This strategy involved a three-fronted approach of 1) Building an international coalition to fight terrorism, 2) Engaging in direct military action against organization engaging in terrorist activities or aiding terrorism and 3) Destroying the sources of finance of these organizations. The most significant operation as part of the Global War on Terror was Operation Enduring Freedom under which the United States Military deposed the Taliban Government from power in Afghanistan which had been providing refuge to Al Qaeda. In addition to operation in Afghanistan, there were operations in Africa, The Philippines and Columbia and in some cases against communist organisations that had no link to Islamic fundamentalism.⁶ This fact exemplifies the actual purpose of the GWOT which was to channelize American anger through military intervention under the alias of the Bush Doctrine which in turn prioritized the exercise of American Imperial power in a unipolar world.⁷

This notion of the need to show power was something that was prevalent in the American Congress as well. The Authorization for the Use of Military Force of 2001 passed by the US Congress within days of the attack on September 18, 2001⁸ is clear evidence of the level of priority that legislators placed on achieving the objective of eradicating terrorism without any regard for the methods with which they are achieved. This idea came to dominate the entire operation and led to decision-making based on created fictional realities as opposed to fact, which in many ways enabled the expedited approval of policies.

Having successfully planned for Phase 1 of the GWOT, the focus of the administration shifted to their long-time enemy Iraq. In a meeting at Camp David, the Deputy Secretary of Defence Paul Wolfowitz, made a case for Iraqi Involvement in the 9/11 attack citing theories that Iraq was behind an attempted hijacking of a Gulf Air Flight and that Ramzi Yousuf, the person behind the 1993 WTC attack was an Iraqi Terrorist. And finally, the decision to invade Iraq was made in the following weeks in spite of a memo sent to the Secretary of State, Condoleezza Rice, which concluded there was “no compelling case that Iraq had either planned or perpetrated the attack.”⁹

Having successfully mobilized troops and capturing Afghanistan from the Taliban by the end of 2001, the focus shifted towards increasing NATO involvement in the GWOT and working towards the long term goals of ensuring a peaceful transition of power to local governments. As the years passed and investment into the war efforts compounded, questions about the effectiveness of the strategy arose, most notably by Donald Rumsfeld himself when he wrote in a memo in October 2003, “Are we winning or losing the Global War on Terror?... Today, we lack metrics to know.... Are we capturing, killing or

⁵ “The Global War on Terrorism: The First 100 Days,” n.d. <https://2001-2009.state.gov/s/ct/rls/wh/6947.htm>.

⁶ “U.S. Military Operations in The Global War on Terrorism: Afghanistan, Africa, The Philippines, And Colombia.” Congressional Research Service, January 20, 2006. <https://crsreports.congress.gov/product/pdf/RL/RL32758/5>.

⁷ Löfflmann, Georg. “The Bush Doctrine redux: changes and continuities in American grand strategy since ‘9/11.’” *International Politics* 61, no. 3 (March 30, 2023): 501–22. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41311-023-00461-9>.

⁸ United States Congress. “Authorization for Use of Military Force.” *Public Law*, 2001. <https://www.congress.gov/107/plaws/publ40/PLAW-107publ40.pdf>.

⁹ Rice. “WARTIME,” n.d. <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/GPO-911REPORT/pdf/GPO-911REPORT-16.pdf>.

deterring and dissuading more terrorists every day than the madrassas and the radical clerics are recruiting, training and deploying against us?”¹⁰ And, even after these questions begun to come up, the war in Iraq did not end till 2011 and US troops were pulled out of Afghanistan in 2021, leaving entire regions destabilized.

Gold et al. argues in evaluating the outcomes of the war that the economic cost to benefit ratio of the GWOT exceed one and that any outcomes with regards to reducing global terrorist activity are difficult to quantify.¹¹ Therefore, this creates a question of incentive in continuing the GWOT for such a long period of time beyond that of revenge, which I believe can be resolved by looking at the political and per capita economic benefits generated by the Military Industrial Complex.

The MIC and the War on Terror:

In the Defence Budgets following the declaration of the GWOT, the amount of expenditure on military contracts rose steadily from 26 billion USD in 2001 to 45 billion USD in 2007, representing an increase of 73% in 6 years.¹² Off the increase in military contracts, the number of no competition contracts, which are contracts offered to a single company without any bidding process, grew by 77% in the stated timeline.¹³ This represents a trend of an increase in contracts that are awarded to companies that possibly had an advantage in setting higher prices. This effect is compounded by government audit reports in the stated period, concluding “insufficient price reasonableness determinations”, thus providing the DoD with plausible deniability with regards to the propagation of an unfair advantage through these contracts.¹⁴

While the increase in no-bid contracts could also be attributed to other factors like the urgency for products or services or could have been the product of the government reallocating funds from running the bidding process to actual operation expenditure, the distribution of contracts reveals another pattern possibly indicating corporate involvement in the decision to increase the number of no competition contracts. In the years after the declaration of the operations, the cost of military contractors awarded to the largest 6 contractors went up from 50 billion USD to 116 billion USD.¹⁵ Looking at this figure along with the fact that in 2003, 9 of the top 10 won a majority of their contracts without bidding,¹⁶

¹⁰ Rumsfeld, Donald H. “The Keeper File.” *Air Force Magazine*, December 2003.

<https://www.airandspaceforces.com/PDF/MagazineArchive/Documents/2003/December%202003/1203keeper.pdf>.

¹¹ Gold, David. “Evaluating the Costs and Benefits of the US War on Terror.” *Eastern Economics Associations*, February 23, 2007.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/24115234_Evaluating_the_Costs_and_Benefits_of_the_US_War_on_Terror.

¹² Ellman, Jesse, David Morrow, and Gregory Sanders. “U.S. Department of Defense Contract Spending and the Supporting Industrial Base,” 2012. https://ciaotest.cc.columbia.edu/wps/csis/0026275/f_0026275_21516.pdf.

¹³ Ibid.

¹⁴ Department of Defense and Office of Inspector General. “FY 2005 DoD Purchases Made Through the General Services Administration.” Report. *Department of Defense Office of Inspector General*, September 30, 2006. <https://media.defense.gov/2006/Oct/30/2001712626/-1/-1/1/07-007.pdf>.

¹⁵ “U.S. Department of Defense Contract Spending And The Supporting Defense Industrial Base.” The Center for Strategic and International Relations, September 2010. https://ciaotest.cc.columbia.edu/wps/csis/0026275/f_0026275_21516.pdf.

¹⁶ Center for Public Integrity. “Center report finds \$362 billion in no-bid contracts at the Pentagon since 1998,” January 8, 2022. <https://publicintegrity.org/national-security/center-report-finds-362-billion-in-no-bid-contracts-at-the-pentagon-since-1998/>.

indicates the possibility of corporate influence within the DoD, which in this case has been used to increase revenue by manipulating the administrative system in their favor.

A major factor that has enabled certain defense contractors to conjure this level of support in the Pentagon is the idea of a “Revolving Door.” This can be defined as, “movement of government personnel into the private sector, and private sector employees into the government¹⁷” and is an issue that is widespread in the defence industry. This phenomena leads to a shift in the mechanism of allocation of resources from competitive markets to political connections, which in turn leads to inefficiency and can be leveraged to reduce oversight in the entire process.¹⁸ The “revolving door” usually takes place in the form of department of defence employees eventually joining executive roles in top defence contractors and leveraging their connections in the pentagon to win contracts for the company.

Another way in which defence contractors win defence contractors in through lobbying agencies. In considering the role that lobbying agencies play in generating business for the MIC, it is important to differentiate between lobbying civil servants in the DoD and politicians in the US congress. In extending the idea of the “revolving door” companies with former high ranking Pentagon Officials in their board of directors or associated with the lobbying agency employed by them, got an increased number of defence contracts following the attack on 9/11. Additionally, the same analysis also found strong positive correlations between the amount spent on lobbying and the presence of a lobbyist from the armed forces with the size of defence contracts received by the company.¹⁹ Larger companies with more access to such connections and lobbying resources will thus, naturally be able to get larger and more number of contracts which aligns with the previous analysis between the size of a defence contractor and the amount they received in defence contracts.

The majority of lobbying, however, is for politicians who can play an important role in shaping the budget that enables the executive branch to create the military contracts. Lobbying firms pay as much as 1 million USD to former congressmen and women to lobby for their clients. This mechanism of lobbying through former representatives is documented to be most effective with companies using former congresspersons winning an average of 3.166 billion USD in contracts compared to an average of 0.203 billion USD won by a firm that does not lobby.²⁰

Another important way in which the MIC is able to influence congresspersons is through campaign funding. Political Action Committee or PACs are the usual instrument by which major defence contractors raise money for political campaigns. The “Big 5” defence contractors all have their own PACs through which they enable their priorities to be legislated on. An analysis of campaign financing by these PAC, which receive millions of dollars in donations, reveals a patter of greater spending on candidates in thee senatorial and congressional races. This reflects a more regional focus of these PACs and desire to win support from a number of politicians on both sides of the political aisle.²¹

¹⁷ Maskell, Jack and Congressional Research Service. “Post-Employment, ‘Revolving Door,’ Laws for Federal Personnel.” Report. Congressional Research Service, January 7, 2014. <https://sgp.fas.org/crs/misc/R42728.pdf>.

¹⁸ Duncan, Thomas K., and Christopher J. Coyne. “The Revolving Door and the Entrenchment of the Permanent War Economy.” *SSRN Electronic Journal*, January 1, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2547996>.

¹⁹ Ağca, Şenay, Deniz Igan, and Bank for International Settlements. “The Lion’s Share: Evidence from Federal Contracts on the Value of Political Connections.” Journal-article. *BIS Working Papers*. Vol. No 1058, December 2022. <https://www.bis.org/publ/work1058.pdf>.

²⁰ Cox, Christian. “Lobbying for government appropriations.” *The RAND Journal of Economics* 54, no. 3 (August 2, 2023): 443–83. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1756-2171.12447>.

²¹ OpenSecrets. “Analysis of Military Industrial Complex PACs,” n.d. <https://www.opensecrets.org/>.

For instance, in the 2004 election cycle the Lockheed Martin PAC donated 9000 USD to Duncan Hunter, A Representative from California. In the congressional term 2005-06, for whose election he received funding from Lockheed Martin, Hunter sponsored the John Warner Defense Authorization Act for the fiscal year 2007, which in turn made provisions for the Army to enter a multi-year contract for the MH-60R helicopters, which are manufactured by Sikorsky which is a subsidiary of Lockheed Martin.²² This Helicopter had parts from other contractors like Northrop Grumman, Thales and Raytheon which represents ways in which contractors produce products that contain parts from different companies increasing overhead costs. And, how they use campaign financing to leverage politicians in the legislature to draft bills that make provisions for the procurement of such products at a greater expense for the treasury. This represents one of many examples in which the military industrial complex uses political connections for its own benefits.

Additionally, military contractors make use of contacts in policy think tanks to generate the initial demand for their products and services. Think tanks like the Heritage Foundation and RAND Cooperation during the War years produced multiple articles and reports outlining the need for increased military spending and upgradation of military hardware. This broadly complies with the priorities of the MIC. Many of these think tanks receive funding from the Defense Contractors, thus, enabling the contractors to indirectly influence decisions made by policy makers and disguise advertising for their products behind the professional recommendations of experts and academics. For example, in 2008, a year in which Lockheed Martin donated 50,000 USD to the Heritage Foundation, the think tank's experts held meetings with executives with Lockheed Martin executives to discuss a strategy for publishing articles to rally congress to approve the continued funding of the F22 Fighter jet in spite of parallel campaigns being run by the secretary of the air force, Michel Donley to stop future funding due to the cost over-runs in its production.²³ Ultimately, a combination of these lobbying techniques led to continued spending on the F22 Raptor till 2011, when it was forced to shut down.²⁴

Military Contractors also typically have a monopoly over spare parts that they sell to the DoD for regular maintenance and repairs. Oversight reports have found cases of these contractors inflating the price for components, which add up to increase the Operating costs of the DoD. The most notable case of this was in 2013 when it was found that Boeing charged the DoD 71.01 USD for a thin metal pin which is usually available in the market for 4 US cents, representing an artificial inflation of cost by 177,475%.²⁵

The Military Industrial Complex makes use of an array of strategies of differing levels of intensity successfully to influence Defense Policy Making to suit its own profit-making motives. While parallels are present in other industries, what sets the MIC apart in terms of the economic costs of such lobbying

²²Congress. "H.R.5122 - John Warner National Defense Authorization Act For Fiscal Year 2007," n.d. <https://www.congress.gov/bill/109th-congress/house-bill/5122>.

²³ Vittori, Jodi and Transparency International Defense & Security Program. "A Mutual Extortion Racket: The Military Industrial Complex and US Foreign Policy - The Cases of Saudi Arabia & UAE." Report. *Transparency International Defense & Security Program*, 2018. https://ti-defence.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/US_Defense_Industry_Influence_Paper_v4_digital_singlePage.pdf.

²⁴ Diaz, Luke. "Was The US Decision To End F-22 Raptor Production A Mistake?" Simple Flying, December 2, 2024. <https://simpleflying.com/was-us-decision-end-f-22-raptor-production-mistake/#:~:text=There%20would%20not%20have%20been,and%20then%20comes%20the%20maintenance!>

²⁵ Office of Inspector General (United States Department of Defense). "Excess Inventory and Contract Pricing Problems Jeopardize the Army Contract With Boeing to Support the Corpus Christi Army Depot." *Program on Government Oversight*, May 11, 2011. <https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/204808-full-unredacted-dod-office-of-inspector-general/>.

is the billions of dollars in contracts that it manages to secure through these techniques and the degree to which such forms of inefficiency impact the government treasury.

There is an argument to be made that the American tax payer in absorbing the costs of such inefficiency will shift their political stance accordingly, therefore, leading to declining political motivations for continuing this misallocation of scarce resources. However, increased defense spending can have much greater positive impacts on the incomes of certain constituents and defense contractors take this factor into account to maximize benefit for voters, thus also reducing incentive for politicians to increase the productivity of defense production.²⁶ Looking at the C17 Globemaster, which is manufactured by Boeing and played a major role in air logistics during the GWOT, had components that were produced by sub-contractors from 42 congressional districts, which generates employment opportunities in these districts and enabling representative to extract political mileage for bringing in industry to the district or state.²⁷ However, the distribution of manufacturing facilities increases transportation costs and is a major factor for cost overruns in military hardware production.

The MIC has created a vicious cycle of mutually beneficial relationships that enable them to get awarded larger defense contracts that increase their revenue and their shareholders' profits. It is estimated that the US Government spends an average of 8.8 billion USD more on defense contracts due to pressure from lobbyists.²⁸ This represents the economic costs to the US treasury and the domestic impact that the MIC has within the United States, but, its impact extends to the realm of foreign policy as well where influence from the complex influenced the degree of aggression in the US's foreign posture during the war.

The MIC's impact on US foreign policy:

Prior to 9/11, US arms sales were a way of rewarding countries that broadly complied with global standards in peace and security management, which also came with strong checks on the accountability of those weapons, but this policy underwent a major shift during the GWOT. The US prioritized the eradication of terrorist groups and to achieve these objectives supplied arms to countries with questionable human rights records like Turkmenistan and did not perform due diligence to ensure that those arms did not fall into the control of enemy combatants.²⁹ The sale of some of the weaponry did go against provisions laid by the Arms Export Control Act and the Foreign Assistance Act and the principle of End-Use Monitoring, laid in these bills, was not usefully implemented most notably when the Government Accountability Office found that Iraqi Security Forces had lost at least 190,000 US Arms in the period between 2003 and 2007.³⁰

²⁶ Reilly, Chandler S. "The Political Economy of Rising Defense Costs." *SSRN Electronic Journal*, January 1, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4369733>.

²⁷ GAO. "DOD PROCUREMENT Geographic Dispersion of C-17 And C-5B Subcontractors." Report. *House of Representatives*, April 12, 1988. <https://www.gao.gov/assets/nsiad-88-123fs.pdf>.

²⁸ "Lobbying for government appropriations." *The RAND Journal of Economics* 54, no. 3 (August 2, 2023): 443–83. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1756-2171.12447>.

²⁹ "Questionable Reward: Arms Sales and the War on Terrorism | Arms Control Association," n.d. <https://www.armscontrol.org/act/2008-01/features/questionable-reward-arms-sales-and-war-terrorism#:~:text=All%20that%20matters%20is%20that,the%20global%20war%20on%20terrorism.&text=To%20be%20sure%2C%20the%20United,willing%20to%20support%20its%20policies.>

³⁰ "GAO-07-711, Stabilizing Iraq: DOD Cannot Ensure That U.S.-Funded Equipment Has Reached Iraqi Security Forces," July 31, 2007. <https://www.gao.gov/assets/a264921.html>.

The nature of these arm sales points to a diversion from the core tenets of American Foreign Policy with limited benefits. Thrall, Cohen and Dorminey et al have argued along similar lines to indicate that post 9/11 arms sales have been largely the product of strategic and economic consideration with little accountability of risk assessment factors.³¹ The military-industry complex has in many ways leveraged this fact to maximize their own profits and to ensure that they out-compete foreign producers.

US Defense Contractors leverage the position of the US as a global hegemon to win defense deals that are parts of larger foreign development aid packages. For example, in the case of Iraq the sale of arms to security forces was structured as a part of a plan to rebuild the country. Additionally, the most lucrative part about arms deals with the US is the fact that it signals strong bilateral relations between the two countries as pointed out by Andrew Shapiro, “When a country acquires an advanced U.S. defence system, they are not simply buying a product to enhance their security, they are also seeking a relationship with the United States. . . . This engagement helps build bilateral ties and creates strong incentives for recipient countries to maintain good relations with the United States.³²” During the GWOT, large arms sales to MENA Countries like the UAE, Qatar and Saudi Arabia by US contractors over other defense contractors like Dassault or Airbus, was at least in part due to the promise of maintaining good relations with the US that the deal promised. This is a method by which US defense contractors can exercise a monopoly over foreign firms.

With foreign arms sale, the defense contractors are able to extract a greater return on Investment as there are no major costs involved in convincing other countries to buy their products. Due to the position of the US in the global World Order, MENA countries like the UAE and Saudi Arabia have their own formidable lobbying operations in the US to convince law makers to continue to supply arms under existing foreign cooperation frameworks.³³ Lobbying both by foreign nations and by US defense contractors has been responsible for increasing the influence of the MIC domestically and internationally, which contributed towards the militarization of America’s policy posture in the 2000’s, but an important consideration that is to be made in understanding the ethical aspects of the MIC, is the extent to which they have affected the dynamics of conflict around the world.

Ethical Implications of the MIC:

The Military Industrial Complex has been overcharging the United States Government and governments of foreign countries by leveraging their position as sole providers of strategic weaponry and by using lobbyists to militarize America’s foreign policy. The vast network of lobbyists that the MIC has created has effectively penetrated the system to ensure that the top players in the defense industry keep winning the Pentagon’s no bid contracts, but these factors do not necessarily imply that the MIC is a cause for global conflict in and of itself. Existing literature criticizing the military-industrial complex for perpetuating conflict, primarily focuses on how they make armed conflict inevitable by increasing the weapons stockpiles of nations and engaging in corrupt practices with politicians.³⁴

³¹ Thrall, A. Trevor, Jordan Cohen, and Caroline Dorminey. “Power, Profit, or Prudence? US Arms Sales since 9/11.” *STRATEGIC STUDIES QUARTERLY*, season-02 2020. https://www.airuniversity.af.edu/Portals/10/SSQ/documents/Volume-14_Issue-2/Thrall.pdf.

³² Thrall, Trevor, and Caroline Dorminey. “Risky Business: The Role of Arms Sales in U.S. Foreign Policy.” CATO Institute, March 18, 2018. <https://www.cato.org/policy-analysis/risky-business-role-arms-sales-us-foreign-policy>.

³³ Vittori, Jodi. “A Mutual Extortion Racket: The Military Industrial Complex and US Foreign Policy - the Cases of Saudi Arabia and the UAE.” Transparency International Defense and Security Program, n.d. https://ti-defence.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/US_Defense_Industry_Influence_Paper_v4_digital_singlePage.pdf.

³⁴ Victoria Uchime, Ozioma. “The roles and consequences of foreign involvement in Nigeria’s internal violent conflicts The roles and consequences of foreign involvement in Nigeria’s internal violent conflicts.” *Cogent Arts & Humanities* 10 (October 14, 2023).

However, an important consideration in analyzing this aspect, is the freedom of a state to make decisions without coercion. While individual politicians are prone to bias and may see personal gain in the quid pro quo relation that the MIC establishes with them, which can lead to a nation purchasing a greater number of weapons at an inflated cost, but just the mere existence of weaponry does not need to force a nation to use these weapons in active combat. Analyzing this argument in the context of the GWOT, the invasion of Iraq, which was championed by Paul Wolfowitz, not out of lobbying by the MIC but because he saw an opportunity to secure US interests by invading Iraq. The fact that the Military Industrial Complex benefited from the decision should be construed as subsidiary to the decision.

Further, The Military Industrial Complex through its lobbying efforts does not sell explicitly sell the idea of war, the focus is purely on arms sales and increasing defense spending which is presented as a strategic and national interest to legislators and government officials. The revenue that they receive from the sale of these weapons is not necessarily different from the sources of revenue of any regular business. If the additional economic benefit received by these companies due to increased military expenditure during active conflict is to be considered, the advantage while admittedly being the greatest for the defense sector is witnessed across all stocks.³⁵ Particularly, goods like steel and coal, which are not directly part of the defense sector, are also found to have reduced volatility in a war economies, thus, making the case for considerable economic gains in non-defense sectors.³⁶

If the definition of the Military-Industrial Complex is expanded to look beyond just producers of defense weaponry to include all services that the US DoD contracts to external agency, the idea of tenable inculpability of the contractor weakens. Private Military Contractor's sell the idea of partaking in active conflict on behalf of sovereign militaries. In such a case, the responsibility of actions taken by the combatants, including civilian harm or engaging in fighting without provocation, fall on the agent within the military industrial complex. For instance, the massacre of 20 Iraqi Civilians by the Private Military Contractor Blackwater in 2007 during a mission to protect state department employees³⁷; this action was carried out under the free agency of Blackwater Employees, a service for which Blackwater had spent 392,000 USD in the same year for lobbying.³⁸

While an argument can be made with regards to the government exercising their own discretion in placing trust in the private military contractor when awarding security contracts, the fact that actual combat action is taken by the agency of another organization whose actions cannot be completely controlled by the government, places the burden of outcome and accountability on the private military contractor. There also questions that can be raised with regards to the extent to which PMCs help governments achieve their long-term goals, as seen in the example of Blackwater where their actions went against the principle of rebuilding Iraq and establishing peace and security which the US hoped to achieve. These conclusions are also broadly echoed by the Council of the European Union –

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/384051307_The_roles_and_consequences_of_foreign_involvement_in_Nigeria's_internal_violent_conflicts_The_roles_and_consequences_of_foreign_involvement_in_Nigeria's_internal_violent_conflicts.

³⁵ Dujava, Cyril, and Radovan Vojtko. "Military Expenditures and Performance of the Stock Markets." *SSRN Electronic Journal*, January 1, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4637610>.

³⁶ National Bureau of Economic Research. "Stock Volatility and the War Puzzle: The Military Demand Channel," 2022. https://www.nber.org/system/files/working_papers/w29837/w29837.pdf.

³⁷ Singer, Peter W. "The Dark Truth about Blackwater." *Brookings*, October 2, 2007. <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/the-dark-truth-about-blackwater/>.

³⁸ OpenSecrets. "Client Profile: Blackwater USA," n.d. <https://www.opensecrets.org/federal-lobbying/clients/lobbyists?cycle=2007&id=D000031985>.

“Accountability issues mean that their effectiveness and their wider impact as a force for peace and stability can also be called into question.³⁹”

The question of accountability of the MIC in the Global War on Terror and more generally in global conflict, depends on the extent to which defense contractors are considered accountable for actions taken by their clients using services or products provided by the contractor. The Military Industrial Complex can be said to catalyze conflict based on the level of accountability placed on them, but in no case can be the cause for the conflict which is determined purely based on the strategic interests of the actors involved. In the case of the GWOT, while elements of the military complex might have resulted in unprovoked conflict, the MIC did not directly lead to increased confrontation with terrorist groups. The methods by which the war was fought, and the outcomes of the operation can be interpreted as a pure consequence of US and NATO defense doctrine.

Conclusion:

In examining the moral culpability of the Military Industrial Complex during the Global War on Terror, the increased economic costs their way of working imposed on the American treasury and their role in perpetuating conflict. From a strictly economic lens, The MIC is overcharging the Pentagon which is leading to a reduction in the number of short- and long-term outcomes achieved by the DoD from spending 1.5 trillion USD from 2001 to 2019.⁴⁰ However, from an ethical point of view, as the MIC in a majority of cases was not directly using or explicitly promoting the use of the weapons they sold, the degree to which they are accountable can be viewed as far lesser than US War Doctrine.

The MIC in Europe played a similar role to that of the US’s in European efforts in the Global War on Terror, albeit in a much smaller capacity. Military Spending in Europe rose during the early years of the war till 2009.⁴¹ The increased spending was used for military procurement for which major contractors like Airbus and Thales lobbied to get the contracts. That being said, anti-lobbying regulations are present in a greater number of EU states and the process of defense contracts is more competitive in Europe.⁴² Further, Europe prioritizing social spending and values over defense spending, often at the expense of combat preparedness, has reduced the extent to which the MIC can build influence.⁴³ This also does go to show how the initial act of prioritizing military spending is a strategic policy taken by a state as opposed to the effect of lobbying.

³⁹ Council of the European Union, “Private Military Companies: Final Report,” August 31, 2023, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/66700/private-military-companies-final-31-august.pdf>.

⁴⁰ “U.S. War Costs, Casualties, And Personnel Levels Since 9/11.” *Congressional Research Service*, April 18, 2019. <https://crsreports.congress.gov/product/pdf/IF/IF11182/1>.

⁴¹ Morcos, Pierre. “Toward a New ‘Lost Decade’? Covid-19 and Defense Spending in Europe,” October 8, 2024. <https://www.csis.org/analysis/toward-new-lost-decade-covid-19-and-defense-spending-europe>.

⁴² Bauer, Elisabeth, Marie Thiel, Irene Chiochetti, Sebastian Kotyla, and Camilla Sante. “Transparency of lobbying in Member States and the UK.” Comparative analysis. European Parliamentary Research Service, 2021. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/EPRS/Lobbying-transparency-comparative-analysis-rev-FINAL.pdf>.

⁴³ COTTARELLI, CARLO, and LEOLUCA VIRGADAMO. “DEFENSE EXPENDITURE IN EU COUNTRIES.” *IEP@BU Policy Brief*, July 2024. https://iep.unibocconi.eu/sites/default/files/media/attach/PB20_%20Defense_2.pdf.

The working of the European MIC can provide a lesson for the US government to deal with the issue of conflict of interests in its MIC. Firstly, there is a desperate need for the adherence to competitive practices in contract allocation. No-bid contracts are enabling defense contracts to artificially inflate their costs and competitive bidding will reduce this effect while also reducing the monopoly of the “Big 5” over the industry. Erik Prince, the founder of Blackwater, pointed out, “Anti-trust enforcement and competitive tenders will stop the corruption of the thousands of lobbyists in Washington milking congress while delivering overpriced and ineffective products.”

Further, Anti-Lobbying Regulation might be effective to a certain degree. While there is strict monitoring in the lobbying process and there is regulation on Campaign Financing, but restrictions on former DoD officials or congressmen joining lobbying organizations might help in making the process of entering the defense industry and winning contracts fairer. Another important step is being more objective about the outcomes of military spending. Greater oversight and a shift in focus to “Quality over Quantity [and] modernization and readiness over size and force structure” might help in reducing the cost to benefit ratio.⁴⁴

As humanity progresses into a highly uncertain and conflict-filled world, Dwight Eisenhower’s warning about the Military Industrial Complex is proving true in multiple conflicts. The paradigm that emerged in the prelude to the Cold War has come to dominate the nature of interaction between the private sector and the government more generally and has had a significant role in impacting defense outcomes domestically and internationally. Reforms to this powerful network between the defense sector and the DoD are essential to improve the efficiency of and achieve positive results from future military policy decisions and actions.

⁴⁴ Miller, James N., and Michael E. O’Hanlon. “Focusing on quality over quantity in the US military budget.” *Brookings*, December 2, 2019. <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/focusing-on-quality-over-quantity-in-the-us-military-budget/>.